

An Analysis of Society Attitude Toward Disable People

- ¹⁻ Sadia Batool, BS Sociology University of Sargodha Sub Campus, Bhakkar Pakistan
²⁻ Salma Raheem, BS Sociology University of Sargodha Sub Campus, Bhakkar Pakistan

Abstract:- Disabilities may include long term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory problem which in interaction with various barrier which may stop their full and affective participation in society. Disability is Damage condition of the body parts and mind, which create hurdles in their daily activities and restrict participation with the other people. The negative attitude built negative society. Negative behavior lead to discourage, lower isolation and self-confidence and as a result negative health impact and thought as a burden on society. Positive attitude shows that people have more knowledge and they accept their disability which effect their behavior. Disable people need support and recognizing their talent to meet their basic goals. This study was conducted in district Bhakkar. University of Sargodha sub campus Bhakkar was selected for study. Simple random sampling technique was used for selection of the respondent. This study based on quantitative research design. In this study questionnaire was conducted as a tool of data collection because majority of respondent literate. Researcher was collected data from the 128 respondent and the selected age of respondent was above from 18 year. The independent variable society attitude shows a positive and statistically strong significant relation with the dependent variable which is disable people. There is a positive ($p < .05$) and strong value among the variables. In this study “an analysis of society’s attitude towards disabled people” we studied that negative attitudes effect disabled people and positive attitudes give positivity in disabled people. Positivity increase their strength, power to do something and increase their morals. At the other hand negative attitudes discourage them, decreases lower isolation and self-confidence. Further study may need to enhance the rights of disabled people. Identifying the practice of educational facilities for disable people. More research is needed in Pakistan on the disabilities studies content.

I. INTRODUCTION

Disabilities may include long term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory problem which in interaction with various barrier which may stop their full and affective participation in society (Thompson, Cannon, & Wickenden, 2020). Disability is Damage condition of the body parts and mind, which create hurdles in their daily activities and restrict participation with the other people (Kivipelto, Mangialasche, & Ngandu, 2018). Different people have different attitude toward disable people, it may be positive or negative. Here we discuss about three school of thought, which states the positive or negative effect, it also discuss about their thoughts, beliefs, ideas and their understanding toward disable people, discuss about behavior in the presence of

referent, (Haegele & Sutherland, 2015). The attitude of the society is different at different place, society built from five pillars which are family, religion, economic, educational and politics. The society contain these pillars and different place contain different attitude (Bansak, Hainmueller, & Hangartner, 2016). Disable people faces the limitation to achieve their goals and restriction for participation in any situation (Adams & Bell, 2016). The people who have the positive attitude toward disable people, they help them and try to remove all their hurdles against disable people (Bunbury, 2020). Positive attitude shows that people have more knowledge and they accept their disability which effect their behavior (Emmers, Baeyens, & Petry, 2020). They have positive social interaction and friendly behavior with disable people (Niemiec, Shogren, & Wehmeyer, 2017). Positive attitude helps him to do work and built their courage for the achievement of goals (Cashman, 2017). Disable people need support and recognizing their talent to meet their basic goals (Adams & Bell, 2016). Sometimes you need to create positive attitude toward disable people for the emergence of healthy society (Roy et al., 2020). Where the disable people live healthy, freely and a place where there dreams comes true (La Follette & Maser, 2019). *Here they need community development and the strong law maker, known as legislation who give them positive services for building their morals (Tzafestas, 2018).*

Where the negative attitude built negative society (Ottoboni et al., 2017). Negative behavior lead to discourage, lower isolation and self-confidence and as a result negative health impact and thought as a burden on society (Swift, Abrams, Lamont, & Drury, 2017). Disable people spend their life under the shadow of sorrows, sadness and leafs of hopelessness (Watts & Luoma, 2020). Negative attitude distract the disable person and they don’t achieve their goals (Dekker, 2017). Sometimes the measurements (visuals) was not correct about disable person, so they don’t reveal truth (Czerniak et al., 2021). Negative attitude discriminate and neglect the disable people (Meisner, 2021). Firstly they experience the negative behavior and second is that they can’t explain their feelings about their condition (Zhao, Chen, Xu, & Zhou, 2022). Some of the main factor which increase the negative behavior toward disable people are people’s knowledge and quality of their relationship and its frequency (French, Allen, & Henderson, 2019).

Some years ago disability thought as a curse in European countries. They didn’t live together with disable people (Papadakaki et al., 2017). They thought that disability is another thing or something coming from another world (Titchkosky, 2020). But now time change and the thoughts of the people also changes (Massey & Whitehead, 2022). Know people help disable people as well as they give them equal

chances in every fields of life, people make NGOs for the help of disable person (Ton, Gaillard, Adamson, Akgungor, & Ho, 2020). But some people also neglect the disable person and push them back (McGillivray, O'Donnell, McPherson, & Misener, 2021). At some point the rights and chances of disabled people get neglected (Shiraani, Shaheer, & Carr, 2022). In Pakistan, different behavior shows than the western countries because of their religion and cultural beliefs (Bukhari et al., 2019). Most of the time disable people faces some difficulties due to the lack of resources, low health facilitate, and shortage of the seats and resources to meet the needs (Whittaker, Wood, Oggero, Kett, & Lange, 2021). Some of the main challenges faced in Pakistan by disable people are health, education, employment, physical access in buildings and transportation are still major challenges (Bakhshi, Babulal, & Trani, 2021). Some normal person avoid, victim the disable people, make different gesture by eyes and face (Maloney, Freeman, & Wohn, 2020). But at the opposite side some people behave normal with disable people as they are normal person which makes them confident, and that positive behavior make them strong to achieve what they may lack in doing by themselves (Drucker, 2017).

The main aim of the study is to analyses the attitude of society towards disable people. The study contains the analysis of society toward physical and mentally disable people, we compare the attitude of same age group of peers, to identify the independent variable of attitude toward disable people.

➤ *Objective*

- Bringing society's attention and behavior at public point with disable people.
- How society behavior and family appreciation with disable people during the phase of education.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *This study was conducted in district Bhakkar.*

University of Sargodha sub campus Bhakkar was selected for study. Simple random sampling technique was used for selection of the respondent. This study based on quantitative research design. In this study questionnaire was conducted as a tool of data collection because majority of respondent literate. Researcher was collected data from the 128 respondent and the selected age of respondent was above from 18 year. Keeping in view the objective of the study, it was decided to take a sample of university students from different departments because there had been no published studies in Bhakkar district. It was a random sampling so neither the information are kept secret, their name, age, department nor any other identifying detailed were sought. The questionnaire prepare for the measurements based on disability. The questionnaire was consist of three main section with 33 questions. The first section is about participants' demographic questions such as age, department and their education. The second section is about the attitude of the societies toward disable people. The third section is about behavior of disable people. Disable people are more exposed for the discrimination in cultural, health and educational aspects of life than normal people. Comparison of discrimination against disable people some years ago and

now. Using SPSS version 21, the collected data were analyzed by using descriptive and regression statistical analysis to examine the relationship between variables such as disabled people and society's attitude. Responses to questioning from the participants views on attitude were related on a 5 point Likert scale ranging from A to E

Table 1: percentage and frequency of the analysis of society's attitude toward disable people concerning the socio demographic characteristics of respondents (n=128)

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Age	18 to 20	42	32.8
	20 to 22	72	56.8
	22 to 25	14	10.9
Gender	Male	54	42.2
	Female	74	57.8
	Transgender	0	0
Department	BBA	18	14.1
	Physics	24	18.8
	Economics	14	10.9
	Social work	14	10.9
	Sociology	16	12.5
	Information technology(I T)	9	7.0
	CS	3	2.3
	English	10	7.8
	Sport science	3	2.3
	psychology	3	2.3
	B. com	14	10.9

Table 1 indicates the percentage and frequency of socio demographic characteristics of respondents. Socio demographic includes gender, age and education of our respondents. In the current study percentage of female respondent was more (57.8%) as compared to male respondents (42.2%). Percentage of 20 to 22 years (56.8%) have more than as compare to 18 to 20 (32.8%) and 20 to 25 (10.9%). The percentage of physics department (18.8%) more than other department as compare to sport science (2.3%), psychology (2.3%), and CS (2.3%) as well.

Table 2: Correlation among dependent (disable people) and independent (attitude of society) (n= 128).

Correlations			
		Independent	Dependent
Independent	Pearson Correlation	1	.387**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	118	118
Dependent	Pearson Correlation	.387**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	118	128

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 indicates correlation between the two main variables used in the current study. It is analyzed from above table that the relationship among the variable was strong and positive. The values of the relationship between independent

and dependent was $r = 0.387$ at $p < 0.01$ depicts the positive relationship among the variables. This means the positive attitude increase leads to increase the behavior with disable people.

Table 3: Model summary among the two variables dependent variable and independent variable. (n=128)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.387 ^a	.150	.142	3.51291
a. Predictors: (Constant), Independent				

Correlation is shown by the r value in the table. The r square value indicates that a unit change in one of the independent variable good affect, the same independent variable by the same unit. according to the table r square value is .150 which indicates that when an independent change the dependent change by .150, thus the variance of .387 is explained by dependent explain by independent variable, the modified r square indicates the population implication of the sample findings. The slight difference between r square and adjusted r square indicates that sample result has highly stronger effect on population.

Table 4: Regression Anova test of dependent variable as disable people and independent variable as society's attitude. (n=128)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	251.960	1	251.960	20.417	.000 ^b
	Residual	1431.506	116	12.341		
	Total	1683.466	117			
a. Dependent Variable: Dependent						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Independent						

Table 4 shows the relationship of dependent variable and independent variable. An Anova test is used to determine whether or not the model fix the data well. When f value exceed 5 and the significant threshold is less than 0.05 the model is considered to be well fitted

Table 5: regression coefficient of dependent variable and independent variable. (n=128)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11.007	1.904		5.782	.000
	Independent	.157	.035	.387	4.519	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Dependent						

The above table is used to calculate the influence of independent factor on the dependent variable i.e. the effect of society on disable people. The independent variable society attitude shows a positive and statistically strong significant relation with the dependent variable which is disable people.

There is a positive ($p < .05$) and strong value among the variables.

III. DISCUSSION

At the end of the 1st year, rehabilitation students had significantly more positive attitude, whereas the business students were more negative. In the 3rd year, these attitude were also found among both groups of students (Lee et al., 2002). This study conducted in china to find out the results of the students who were rehabilitated on the negative behavior with disable people. After rehabilitation the results were different, mostly students have negative attitude than they started a technique in which they take two group of 1st year students and 3rd year students, in which 1st year students rehabilitated about disability and disable people and 3rd year students who will not rehabilitated, result was different as 1st year students change their attitude as they have positive attitude and 3rd year students have negative attitude as they had not rehabilitated. This study shows that the attitude of the people changes with the passage of time, knowledge and awareness.

Pakistan is the religious country and the people of Pakistan are more kind with every one especially with disable people. They give extra sympathy and extra ordinary care to the disable people. Their behavior shows more positivity toward disable people. In the introduction it was argued that the attitude of society are related to behavior toward disable people. With the limits of method used this study shows that the attitude of selected people have strong and positive attitude toward disabled people. This current study conducted in Pakistan which shows the strong and positive attitude toward disable people. They are more helpful and they have normal behavior with disable people as with other normal human being.

Another result should be the difference as the article "the effect of disability empathy activity on the attitude of nursing students towards disabled people". Shows the result as the before the experiment there was no significant difference between ATDP (Attitude Towards Disable Person) scores of experimental and control group ($p > 0.05$). After the experiment, second ATDP score of experimental group (66.81 ± 14.27) were found to be significantly higher than the score of control group (59.02 ± 11.71) ($p = 0.002$). After six month, third ATDP scores of experimental group (63.58 ± 13.46) were also found to be higher than the scores of control group (58.43 ± 11.03) ($p = 0.025$) (Geçkil, Kaleci, Cingil, & Hisar, 2017). This study shows that there are two main group which are experimental group and control group, the scores of control group (58.43 ± 11.03) ($p = 0.025$) and the scores of experimental group (63.58 ± 13.46) which shows that the experimental group have positive affect regarding disability and control group have less effect after experiment. That study was conducted in France and they have different norms and values where they don't help disable people but after experiment they change their mind. They make two group which are "experiment group" and "control group" the experimental group have higher value than the control group after an experiment.

In current study the rate of ($r= 0.387$ at $p<0.01$) depicts that the study have positive and strong effect on disability. People are more concern with disable people and get attached with their feelings when they spend some time. Pakistan is the religious country and the Pakistani people follows their norms and values. To give respect the disable people taught our religion therefore current study contain positive and strong relation with disabled people. The main important thing is that society get aware from the importance of disable people, therefore the people change their attitude toward disabled people with the passage of time. When people get more knowledge and have a sense of behavior than they to change their attitude from negative to positive.

That study have total different results from current study, the reason may be that, in 2017 when the study conducted people have less awareness and knowledge. They don't understand as the member of society, even they thought that the disable people was something another thing which is not the part of human beings. But currently, in 2022 people have change their attitude the reason might be that they have more knowledge, awareness and the most important thing is that we learnt that behavior with disable people from our norms, culture and religion. Both studies have different place of experiment that study contains nurse's attitude toward disable people which is the part of society, but current study contain different students and people belong to society. These are the main reason might be that both studies have different behavior and result.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study "an analysis of society's attitude towards disabled people" we studied that negative attitudes effect disabled people and positive attitudes give positivity in disabled people. Positivity increase their strength, power to do something and increase their morals. At the other hand negative attitudes discourage them, decreases lower isolation and self-confidence. But society have awareness about disable people and they know that how to behave with them therefore, findings shows positive and strong relation, which depicts that know the society have positive attitude toward disabled people. Members of society (people) believe that a disabled person "can be productive member of society, they make their own decision and live like a normal human being", in the other words having positive attitudes toward disabled people may develop the quality of society's care given to them.

RECOMMENDATION

Further study may need to enhance the rights of disabled people. Identifying the practice of educational facilities for disable people. More research is needed in Pakistan on the disabilities studies content. The people might be studies and focus on the care and treatment on their community specially recommended essential for maintaining high quality of care.

RESEARCH LIMITATION AND STRENGTH

Utilizing a small number of students in the sample and restricting the study to 128 university students limit the generalizability of the results.

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